

Multi-band Microwave Sensor based on Hilbert's Fractal for Dielectric Solid Material Characterization

C. P. do N. Silva^{1,2*}, J. A. I. Araujo¹, M. S. Coutinho¹, M. R. T. de Oliveira¹, I. Llamas-Garro² and M. T. de Melo¹

¹ Department of Electronic and System, Universidade Federal de Pernambuco, UFPE, Recife, Brasil.

² Centre Tecnològic de Telecomunicacions de Catalunya, CTTC/CERCA, Barcelona, Spain.

*crislanepns@gmail.com

Abstract: A planar sensor designed using the fourth Hilbert fractal curve iteration for solid material characterization at multiple frequencies is reported in this paper. The fractal curve is self-similar with space filling properties. The Hilbert fractal geometry is used to form a compact resonator, with a multiband frequency response where miniaturization is achieved, since a large transmission line length is effectively confined in a limited area. The sensor provides five resonances in the frequency range from 0 to 5 GHz. The resonant frequencies are 0.56, 1.68, 2.72, 3.69 and 4.72 GHz, all used to measure the real permittivity of known samples with a sensitivity of 7, 20, 27, 43 and 50 MHz/permittivity, respectively. The sensor is used to measure dielectric samples with 20 x 20 mm² areas with several thicknesses. Simulations and measurements demonstrate that the Hilbert fractal geometry can be used to design a multiband planar sensor for solid dielectric material characterization.

Index terms: Microwave sensor, fractal geometry, multiband sensing, resonator, dielectric substrates.

1. Introduction

Nowadays it is possible to find several types of microwave-based sensors for diverse applications [1], such as liquid biological and chemical tests [2,3], food and agricultural products [4,5], and measurements of industrial materials [6,7].

Planar and hollow waveguides are commonly used for microwave sensor design, mainly in the range between 1 and 20 GHz. A broadly used planar structure is the microstrip line [8]. The microstrip structures are composed of a conductive strip, a dielectric substrate, and a ground plane. When employed in sensors, transmission and reflection techniques are used to characterize materials [9].

When microstrip transmission lines are designed for material characterization sensors, resonant or non-resonant structures can be applied. Resonant methods are preferable because they have greater precision and sensitivity [8]. One of these methods is known as resonant disturbance, based on detecting the frequency

resonance shift of the microstrip resonator when measuring a sample [10]. The concept of planar microstrip sensors has been developed in the early 1970s, resulting in the first commercial sensors for food processing, as well as for measuring fruit maturation and moisture content [4].

The use of a fractal geometry results in a reduction of sensor dimensions with improved sensitivity, due to its intrinsic properties: self-similarity, infinite complexity, and small dimensions with space filling properties. The term fractal characterizes objects whose parts resemble the whole structure, thus as the visualization scale increases or decreases, its shape is not altered, remaining identical or very similar to the original structure [11]. Currently fractal structures are used in several microwave applications such as the development of compact interferometers based on Hilbert's fractal geometry [12], fractal phase shifters [13] or resonators for filter miniaturization [14].

In this paper, a planar sensor for real permittivity characterization is proposed, and used to sense well-known dielectric substrates to demonstrate its multiband sensing properties with small dimensions. The sensor has five resonant frequencies at 0.56, 1.68, 2.72, 3.69 and 4.72 GHz, all of them suitable to measure the real permittivity with a sensibility of 7, 20, 27, 43 and 50 MHz/permittivity, respectively. To the best of the authors' knowledge, there is no multiband sensor with 5 bands for dielectric material characterization in the literature. In [15], a multiband sensor with 4 bands is described, however the design uses four different resonators, one per band, resulting in the need of large sample dimensions. The proposed sensor has just one resonator and requires smaller material samples with an area of 20 x 20 mm².

This paper is broken down into the following sections: Section II describes the Hilbert Fractal geometry. Section III describes the sensor implementation. Section IV contains the experimental demonstration using the proposed sensor and section V provides an overall conclusion to this work.

2. The Hilbert fractal geometry

The German mathematician David Hilbert introduced the Hilbert fractal curve in 1981. It is a space filling, self-similar continuous curve that fills space without intersecting itself. The first four iterations of the Hilbert fractal curve are shown in Fig. 1. As one can see, as the total length increases, the total area occupied by the fractal structure remains the same. This characteristic is important for the proposed sensor design since a multiband behavior is obtained, where the coupling between adjacent lines increases the capacitance of the sensor, and consequently its sensibility.

In each subsequent iteration, the resonator length ideally doubles with respect to its previous iteration. In theory, the length of the resonator tends to infinity in a limited area for infinite iterations, however in practice, narrow transmission lines become impractical for high order iterations.

The space-filling Hilbert fractal curve is used as a resonator to design a multiband sensor to measure the dielectric constant of dispersive materials. The multiband response is due to higher resonance frequencies of the resonator which are well defined. The long length required to achieve more resonances is confined in a constant area, thus resulting in a miniaturized sensor. Any fractal curve with space-filling properties, such as the Peano and Moore fractals, can be used. However, future studies must be done to evaluate how different types of fractal structures affect the sensor response.

Fig. 1 The first four Hilbert fractal iterations occupying the same area.

3. Sensor design

Fig. 2 shows the microstrip sensor layout using the fourth Hilbert fractal curve iteration as a resonator for its design. The shaded areas correspond to copper microstrip lines patterned on a substrate. The sensor is designed using an AD1000™ substrate with dielectric constant of 10.2, loss tangent of 0.0004 and thickness of 1.27 mm. The ports are designed to have a characteristic impedance of 50 Ohms. Here, the fourth iteration of the Hilbert fractal curve is utilized with an approximate length (l_{ef}) of 243 mm, occupying an area of 400 mm².

The fourth iteration is chosen because it provides a good trade-off between using a large resonator length, while obtaining an appropriate coupling between lines, all confined in a small area for multiband sensing.

The fundamental resonant frequency (f_1) of the proposed multiband sensor can be calculated using eq.1 [16].

$$f_1 \text{ (GHz)} = \frac{0.3}{l_{ef} \sqrt{\epsilon_{reff}}} \quad (1)$$

The effective dielectric constant ϵ_{reff} (AD1000™, $w = 0.3 \text{ mm}$) = 6.35, and $l_{\text{ef}} \approx \lambda_{\text{g}1}$, where $\lambda_{\text{g}1}$ is the guided wavelength for f_1 . The resonator also resonates at higher frequencies when $f_n \approx (2n - 1)f_1$. Table I shows the calculated and simulated fundamental resonance frequency of the multiband sensor. This also means that the resonant frequencies are separated from each other by $2f_1 \approx (f_n - f_{n-1})$.

The sensor principle of operation consists in the fact that although the electric field is more concentrated between the lines of the microstrip and the ground, there is a weaker field above the substrate. Therefore, the ϵ_{reff} calculation considers the substrate and the material above the substrate (sample). When some sample is placed above the resonator, ϵ_{reff} changes and hence the resonant frequencies changes. The sample not only causes a resonant frequency shift towards lower frequencies, but also a change in resonator quality factor towards lower Q-values [17]. Sensor strips are arranged to follow Hilbert's fractal for device miniaturization and a multi-band response, resulting in perpendicular microstrips to form the resonator, thus, the proposed device is not suitable for anisotropy sample measurements [18].

Fig. 2 Sensor layout design based on the fourth iteration of the Hilbert fractal curve.

Table I. Calculated and simulated first resonant frequency of the multiband sensor.

Resonance (GHz)	Calculated	Simulated	Measured
f_1	0.49	0.56	0,58
f_2	1,68	1,68	1,73
f_3	2,80	2,72	2,84
f_4	3,92	3,69	3,88
f_5	5,04	4,72	4,92

4. Simulated and measured results

The Hilbert's fractal sensor is simulated using a 3D electromagnetic software, the structure used for simulations is shown in Fig. 3. Simulated and measured results are presented in Fig. 4, and consist of $|S_{21}|$ (dB) in the frequency range from 0.1 to 5 GHz, according to a sensor with no sample on top of it. The sensor without sample presents five resonance frequencies at 0.56, 1.68, 2.72, 3.69 and 4.72 GHz. Table II summarizes the resonance frequency, quality factor and bandwidth (in relation to -10 dB values) for the sensor without sample. It is apparent from Fig. 4 and table II that the resonance frequencies have similar characteristics such as high quality factors, bandwidths in the range from 210 to 290 MHz and return losses over 30 dB.

The sensor operation is based on the premise that all existing materials have a specific dielectric permittivity at RF and microwave frequencies. The electric field is mainly concentrated in the substrate, but there is still an electric field component above the substrate. Thus, when a material is placed on top of the resonator, the effective permittivity will vary and thus the resonance frequency of the sensor will shift.

Fig. 3 Sensor schematic used for simulations, including a dielectric sample on top of the sensor.

Fig. 4 Simulated frequency response of the fractal sensor with no sample.

Table 2. Simulated resonance frequency characteristics of the sensor without sample.

Resonance Frequency	Quality Factor	Bandwidth (-10 dB)
0.56 GHz	417.80	0.29 GHz
1.68 GHz	143.40	0.26 GHz
2.72 GHz	160.20	0.28 GHz
3.69 GHz	442.25	0.21 GHz
4.72 GHz	375.50	0.27 GHz

Sample thickness is an important parameter, taken into account in the measurement and simulation technique to find the dielectric constant. This technique is described in [9]. Simulation results showed that even a thin 100 μm thick sample can be detected. Frequency shifts on the five resonant frequencies happens for low-loss sample materials with high dielectric constants up to 100. In this paper, dielectric loss is not measured, however using perturbation theory techniques; the proposed sensor can be used to measure dielectric losses, by measuring the quality factor.

To simulate the sensor with the sample, a parallelepiped piece of material measuring 20 x 20 x t mm³ is placed over the area containing the fractal resonator, where the highest concentration of electric field is found, t is the thickness of the simulated samples, in specific 1.5, 3.048, 3.2, 3.810, 2.54 mm according to the permittivity of 2.2, 2.94, 4.5, 10.2 and 10.8, respectively.

Thus, the relative permittivity sample values are varied between 1 (bare sensor, without sample) and 10.8. Fig. 5 contains the simulated insertion loss results for the sensor with samples on top. The resonant frequency shift is apparent and according to sample relative permittivity variation.

Fig. 6 analyzes dielectric permittivity variation as a function of sensor resonance frequency for the device five frequencies of operation. The curves obtained show a high degree of linearity. Through a linear fit of simulated data, equations show that the sensitivity obtained is 10, 35, 54, 86 and 97 MHz/permittivity, according to resonant frequencies one to five, respectively.

The higher frequencies are proportional to the fundamental one by the factor $2n - 1$. So, considering the simplest case where ϵ_r is constant, a shift in f_1 , $\Delta f_{1\epsilon_r}$, causes a shift in f_n , $\Delta f_{n\epsilon_r} \approx (2n - 1)\Delta f_{1\epsilon_r}$. The sensitivity (S_{f_1}) of f_1 can also be calculated by solving $S_{f_1} = \frac{\Delta f_{1\Delta\epsilon_{r_{i,k}}}}{\Delta\epsilon_{r_{i,k}}}$, where $\Delta\epsilon_{r_{i,k}}$ is the difference between the lowest (i) and highest (k) dielectric constant value that the sensor can detect, and $\Delta f_{1\Delta\epsilon_{r_{i,k}}}$ is the first resonance shift according to the sample measured. That is, knowing the sensitivity of the fundamental resonant frequency, the sensitivity of the following resonances are well defined ($S_{f_n} = (2n - 1)S_{f_1}$) and always higher than the fundamental one.

Fig. 5 Fractal sensor simulated results for real permittivity variation from 1 to 10.8.

Fig. 6 Relation between the relative permittivity and resonant frequencies obtained through simulations. f_1 corresponds to the first resonance frequency and f_5 corresponds to the fifth resonance frequency, accordingly.

The sensor prototype is manufactured using an Everprecision® EP2006H machine, and has the overall dimensions provided in Fig. 7. The $|S_{21}|$ (dB) experimental results are obtained using a Keysight® N9952A portable VNA.

The measurement setup consists of connecting the sensor through SMA connectors to the network analyzer and measuring the insertion loss values in the range from 0.1 to 5 GHz. The measurements are performed with samples made of substrates with known permittivity values, including the bare sensor with no sample. The measured samples are formed using piled substrate layers with different thicknesses. The substrate layers are placed one above another to achieve the given sample thickness provided in Table III.

The measurement setup is shown in Fig. 8, for a sensor with a sample on top. Table III lists the samples used in the experiment and Fig. 9 contains the experimental results obtained. Fig. 4, shows a comparison between the simulated and measured insertion loss response for the sensor with no sample, where the results are in good agreement. The measured results show five resonant frequencies. All the resonances present a small shift compared to the simulated results. The fifth resonance has the larger shift of 214 MHz.

Fig. 7 Photograph of the fabricated compact planar fractal sensor.

Table 3. Samples used for measurements.

Substrates	Permittivity	Substrate layer thickness (mm)	Samples thickness (mm)
RO6010	10.80	0.635	2.540
AD1000	10.20	3.000	3.000
FR-4	4.50	1.600	3.200
RO6002	2.94	1.524	3.048
Duroid 5880	2.20	0.750	1.500

Fig. 8 Experimental setup.

Fig. 9 Measured results for samples with different permittivity values and the bare sensor without sample

It is apparent from Fig. 9 that when a sample is deposited on top of the sensor, there is a resonance frequency shift according to the permittivity of the sample being measured, observed as different magnitudes of the transmission coefficient in $|S_{21}|$ (dB) at a given frequency. The resonance frequency variations are adequate to distinguish each sample, where the sensitivity increases as the frequency of operation increases. Fig. 11 shows the variation in dielectric permittivity as a function of resonance frequency for each of the five operating frequencies, obtained through linear regression of measurement data. The measured results present a high degree of linearity and a sensitivity of 7, 20, 27, 43 and 50 MHz, for the five resonance frequencies, respectively.

The sensitivities obtained from measurements differ from the simulated ones because there are air gaps formed between the substrate layers that compose the sample, and an air gap formed between the resonator and the sample. However, the expected resonant frequency shift behavior is observed according to each sample, making the proposed sensor adequate to characterize dielectric samples using the five different resonant frequencies with good sensitivity and small size.

A high dielectric constant substrate is used for this sensor design to achieve sensor miniaturization and allow small sensor samples to be measured, with the tradeoff of lower sensor sensitivity. Higher sensor sensitivity values can be achieved using a lower dielectric constant substrate to make the sensor or the use of coplanar interdigital lines.

Table 4 shows a comparison between the proposed sensor and other dielectric sensors available in the literature. In [15], the authors present a multiband sensor with four different resonances and good sensitivity. Four resonators are designed, one for each resonant frequency, which makes the sensor large compared to the proposed implementation. The required sample is large, since it must cover all resonators for multiband sensing. In [17] the authors present a microstrip ring resonator with high sensitivity but just with one resonant frequency. In [19], a metamaterial structure with two resonant frequencies is proposed, however just one resonance is used to measure the real permittivity of a sample. In this work, a small sensor with five resonant bands is proposed. The sensor presents good quality factors and needs a small sample. All five resonances have good sensitivity for dielectric material characterization using multiband sensing. Ways to increase the sensitivity of the proposed sensor include using a lower dielectric constant substrate to make the sensor, or the use of coplanar transmission lines. In both cases, more electric field will penetrate the sample, resulting in increased sensor sensitivity.

Fig. 10 Relation between the relative permittivity and resonant frequencies obtained through measurements. f_1 corresponds to the first resonance frequency and f_5 corresponds to the fifth resonance frequency.

Table 4. Comparison of dielectric material sensors available in the literature.

Ref.	N ^o of resonant bands	f_r (GHz)	Size (mm)	Sample Size (mm)	Sensitivity (GHz/ ϵ_r)	Q factor	Technology
[15]	4	1.5, 2.45, 3.8 and 5.8	Not presented Large sensor	Not presented (almost the size of the sensor)	0.9	Not presented	Microstrip (Ring resonator on ground plane)
[17]	1	2.22	68.30 x 71.84	25 x 17	0.652	652.94	Microstrip (split ring resonator)
[19]	2	4.9, 9.30	20 x 20	20 x 20	0.44	Not presented	Metamaterial structure
This work	5	0.56, 1.68, 2.72, 3.69 and 4.72	40 x 28	20 x 20	0.007, 0.022, 0.027, 0.043 and 0.05	417.8, 143.4, 160.2, 442.2, 375.5	Fractal resonator

5. Conclusions

The Hilbert fractal curve is used in the design and construction of a small size microwave planar sensor to characterize low loss materials with relative permittivity ranging from 1 to 10.8, and according to simulations the sensor can be used to measure dielectric constants up to 100. The results show that the Hilbert fractal-based sensor presents a multiband response with an adequate quality factor and transmission loss for sensing. The sensor has been designed on a high dielectric constant substrate to achieve miniaturization with the trade-off of having a lower sensor sensitivity. Sensor sensitivity can be increased by using a lower dielectric constant material to make the sensor or by using coplanar interdigital transmission lines. When samples are placed on top of the sensor, the capacitance of the structure varies, and therefore, a resonance frequency shift is observed in the sensor response. The proposed sensor operates with five resonance frequencies in the range from 0.1 to 5 GHz, namely 0.56, 1.68, 2.72, 3.69 and 4.72 GHz. The highest sensor resonance frequency of operation presented the highest sensitivity. The sensor has small dimensions with a multiband response and consequently requires small sample dimensions. The results obtained indicate that the proposed compact and low-cost fractal sensor is suitable for measuring dispersive low-loss samples using multiband sensing. Future work involves analysing the response and sensitivity of sensors using other fractal structures with self-filling properties.

6. Acknowledgments

This work is supported by the Spanish government under MICINN grant RTI2018-099841-B-I00. Part of this work has been supported by the Generalitat de Catalunya under grant 2017 SGR 891 and CAPES PDSE 47/2017 from the Brazilian government.

7. References

- [1] Skulski, J., Galwas, B. A.: 'Planar resonator sensor for moisture measurements'. 12th International Conference on Microwaves and Radar, Kraków, Poland, May 1998, pp. 692-695
- [2] Galwas, B. A., Piotrowski, J. K., Skulski, J.: 'Dielectric measurements using a coaxial resonator opened to a waveguide below cut-off'. IEEE Transactions on Instrumental and Measurement, 1997, 46, (2), pp. 511-514
- [3] Galwas, B. A., Piotrowski, J. K., Skulski, J.: 'New type of microwave resonator sensors with waveguide below cut-off'. 1996 Conference on Precision Electromagnetic Measurements Digest, Braunschweig, Germany, Aug 1996, pp. 76-77
- [4] Yeow, Y. K., Jalani, S. N. A., Abbas, Z., Ling, Y. L.: 'Application of bandpass filter as a sensor for rice characterization'. 2010 Int. Conf. on Comp. Applications and Ind. Electronics (ICCAIE), Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia, Dec 2010, pp. 570-573

- [5] El Sabbagh. A. M., Ramahi. M. O., Trabelsi. S., Nelson. O. S., Khan. L.: 'Use of Microstrip Patch Antennas in Grain Permittivity Measurement'. 2003 Instrumentation and Measurement Technology Conference (IMTC), Colorado, USA, May 2003, pp. 640-644
- [6] Fericean. S., Dorneich. A., Droxler. D., Krater. D.: 'Development of a Microwave Proximity Sensor for Industrial Applications'. IEEE Sensors Journal, 2009, 9, (7), pp. 870-876
- [7] Fericean. S., Dorneich. A., Droxler. D., Krater. D.: 'Development of a Microwave Proximity Sensor for Industrial Applications'. 2008 IEEE Sensors, Lecce, Italy, Dec 2008, pp. 1402-1405
- [8] Bogner, Andreas et al. Planar microstrip ring resonators for microwave-based gas sensing: Design aspects and initial transducers for humidity and ammonia sensing. Sensors Journal, v. 17, n. 10, p. 2422, 2017.
- [9] Coutinho, Marcelo S. et al. Planar sensor for powder grain characterization. IET Microwaves, Antennas & Propagation, v. 12, n. 10, p. 1666-1670, 2018.
- [10] Chen, Lin-Feng et al. Microwave electronics: measurement and materials characterization. John Wiley & Sons, 2004.
- [11] M. A. H. Ansari, A. K. Jha, Z. Akhter and M. J. Akhtar, "Multi-Band RF Planar Sensor Using Complementary Split Ring Resonator for Testing of Dielectric Materials," in IEEE Sensors Journal. 18 (16), 6596-6606, 2018.
- [12] C. P. N. Silva, E. M. F. de Oliveira, M. R. T. de Oliveira, M. T. de Melo and B. G. M. de Oliveira, "New compact interferometer based on fractal concept," 2015 SBMO/IEEE MTT-S International Microwave and Optoelectronics Conference (IMOC), Porto de Galinhas, 2015, pp. 1-3.
- [13] E. M. F. de Oliveira, L. P. Pontes, C. P. N. Silva, M. T. de Melo, B. G. M. de Oliveira and I. Llamas-Garro, " Microstrip fractal-based phase shifter an UHF phase shifter based on with Hilbert's fractal delay lines," 2017 47th European Microwave Conference (EuMC), 2017, pp. 1148-1150.
- [14] P. Jarry, J. Beneat e E. Kerherve, "Fractal microwave filters," 2010 IEEE 11th Annual Wireless and Microwave Technology Conference (WAMICON), Melbourne, FL, 2010, pp. 1-5.
- [15] M. Arif Hussain Ansari, Student Member, IEEE, Abhishek Kumar Jha, Member, IEEE, Zubair, Akhter, Member, IEEE and M. Jaleel Akhtar, Senior Member, IEEE, "Multi-Band RF Planar Sensor Using Complementary Split Ring Resonator for Testing of Dielectric Materials", IEEE Sensors Letters, 2018
- [16] Neto, A. G., Goncalves da Costa, A., & da Silva Moreira, C. (2017). A New Planar Sensor Based On The Matryoshka Microstrip Resonator. 2017 SBMO/IEEE MTT-S International Microwave and Optoelectronics Conference (IMOC). doi:10.1109/imoc.2017.8121074
- [17] Alahnomi, R. A., Zakaria, Z., Ruslan, E., Ab Rashid, S. R., & Mohd Bahar, A. A. (2017). High-Q Sensor Based on Symmetrical Split Ring Resonator with Spurlines for Solids Material Detection. IEEE Sensors Journal, 17(9), 2766–2775. doi:10.1109/jsen.2017.2682266
- [18] Morales-Lovera, H.-N., Olvera-Cervantes, J.-L., Corona-Chavez, A., & Kataria, T. K. (2019). Dielectric Anisotropy Sensor Using Coupled Resonators. IEEE Transactions on Microwave Theory and Techniques, 1–7. doi:10.1109/tmtt.2019.2958265

- [19] Islam, M. T., Rahman, M. N., Mahmud, M. Z., Ullah, M. A., Samsuzzaman, M., & Singh, M. J. (2018). Investigation of a resonator-based metamaterial for sensor applications. *Applied Physics A*, 124(2). doi:10.1007/s00339-017-1544-7